

Addressing the complexity of bridging thermal and reactive catalysis. The role of strong localised electrical fields.

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Abstract

Reactive (photo, electro and plasma) catalysis requires the development of new concepts and approaches that are different from those in use for thermal catalysis, while the common practice is to translate methodologies and modelling from thermal to reactive catalysis. This perspective contribution aims to shed light on the difference between them because their understanding is a conditioning factor in accelerating the progress of reactive catalysis. They play a crucial role in developing technologies for low-carbon chemical production. Emphasis is given to the role of strong localised electrical fields (LEF) generated by the coupling of charges with localised phonon modes, i.e. catalyst vibrations. They play a role in low-temperature catalytic processes, typical of reactive catalysis, which is different from higher-temperature conditions (thermal catalysis). The role of the electrical field in catalytic processes is an emerging area, influencing the chemisorption and surface mobility of adspecies. However, LEFs play a more critical role because they determine the rate and selectivity of the reaction. They are a distinct feature which differentiates reactive from thermal catalysis and, thus, a key feature for their understanding and modelling. However, it is an area still largely unexplored. We discuss some case examples and concepts related to photocatalytic water splitting on TiO₂ (showing that the water layer restructures in the presence of an electric field), the generation of LEFs and relation to electrode nanostructure, as well as their importance to understanding electro-catalysis, and the consequent need to include these aspects in a new modelling approach. The examples provide evidence that explains why new concepts and models are required for reactive catalysis. The discussion spotlights the difference with respect to thermal catalysis and aims to stimulate researchers to view reactive catalysis from a novel research perspective.

1. Introduction

Understanding surface mechanisms in heterogeneous catalysis has undoubtedly made very large advances in recent years [1]. However, driven by the quest to electrify chemical production to substitute fossil fuels progressively [2-4], photo-, electro- and plasma catalytic technologies (called reactive catalysis trio hereinafter) have progressively become a dominant research topic [5-7]. An acceleration in their development is needed to meet targets such as net-zero emissions by 2050 [6] and objectives such as carbon circularity [8] and a sustainable green future [9].

The design and mechanistic approaches for developing these "reactive" catalysts are essentially based on adapting the approaches used in heterogeneous catalysis [10,11]. There are several evident differences between reactive and thermal catalysis, from the different temperature ranges of operations (in an electrocatalytic reaction, the reactivity should be negligible at zero potential, i.e. in the absence of charge generation) to the presence of charges on the surface induced by the application of a potential or charge separation (by light absorption in a semiconductor) or by interaction with the catalyst of charged species generated by non-thermal plasma. However, the inspection of the many reviews on reactive catalysis mechanisms (limiting to a few examples for electrocatalysis [12-19]) clearly indicates how these differences are not specifically accounted and the mechanisms and design criteria do not differentiate substantially with respect to thermal catalysis in the majority of cases.

We proposed this term of reactive catalysis to differentiate photo-, electro- and plasma catalytic technologies from heterogeneous thermal catalysis, where heat is the source of energy to overcome the activation barriers. The mechanism is instead different in reactive catalysis, as clarified further below. Thus, there is an intrinsic mechanistic difference. Fostering the understanding of this reactive catalysis trio is crucial to open new possibilities and directions in unconventional catalysis [20]. Still, it requires understanding the differences between thermal and reactive catalysis and whether our conventional approaches to modelling and mechanistic study of heterogeneous catalysis have to be revised or not. Further aspects are commented on below.

This contribution analyses whether current approaches in mechanistic analysis and the design of reactive catalysts could identify the crucial parameters for designing them. Many reviews, a limited selection of which is reported in the following references [21-29], claim this possibility. It is typically not even questioned if there are limitations in the approach or if the fundamentals have to be revised.

For example, the volcano approach, e.g. the Sabatier principle that the interactions between the catalyst and the reactants should be neither too strong nor too weak, leading to a maximum in the rate as a function of a design parameter (such as the heat of adsorption), is the fundament of catalysis. It is at the core of modelling approaches to catalysis [30,31]. It is used to estimate and predict the dependence of the performance of a catalyst from one or more descriptor variables while establishing scaling relationships that relate the binding energies of a wide variety of catalytic

intermediates across a range of catalyst surfaces [32-36]. Thus, it is a key tool for catalyst design and is widely applied also in electrocatalysis [37-41].

Many papers discuss how to break the volcano-plot limits and report performances beyond the maximum predictions [42-47]. The approaches to describe strategies and performances beyond theoretical limits are mainly based on an extension of modelling tools, while the fundamentals of the approach and methodology (mainly based on density functional theory – DFT and its extensions) are not questioned. There are many simplifications in the modelling approach, from the surface coverage and related induced reconstructions on the active sites to other relevant aspects not considered, in addition to the intrinsic limitations in the DFT approach. However, in part, the latter aspects are addressed in modern improvements of the theory [48,49].

The question is whether the simplification needed for the modelling approach and related mechanistic and design interpretations are valid or, instead, have intrinsic limitations on the capability to predict the behaviour in relevant catalysts and operation conditions. Is there a limit by which the current modelling approaches cannot properly account for the complexity of the behaviour? In other words, they are still a valid designing tool?

From an experimental perspective, we remarked on the limits of current mechanistic approaches, including theoretical modelling, by analysing the literature data for electrocatalytic fixation of N₂ to ammonia [50] and CO₂ methanation [51]. They are unable to properly identify design rules that are valid beyond the specific system under study.

In fact, in these two target electrocatalytic reactions, over ten significantly different mechanisms and key features for the active sites were identified on a selected homogeneous class of electrocatalytic materials, giving essentially similar catalytic performances from a bird-eye view compared to performances required for application. The mechanistic conclusions were based on the integration of experimental and modelling data. However, completely different mechanistic indications for analogous samples giving very similar catalytic performances put a question mark on the results. The conclusion was that often in electrocatalysis, particularly under experimental conditions relevant for (industrial) application [52,53], the current mechanistic approaches are unable to catch the effective factors determining the performances and thus properly identify the design criteria.

It is necessary to note that due to the complexity of catalysis, a single design framework for all catalysis is (likely) unrealistic or, better yet, too highly challenging. However, it is also true that when the "design" of catalysts is claimed (as in many papers), it must be valid beyond too specific cases and be a tool to develop better and novel catalysts. Thus, the question remains of whether, in reactive (electro) catalysis, the application of methodologies translated from thermal catalysis is an effective tool for progress in this field. A related question, which is discussed in this perspective contribution, is whether there are alternative approaches to those used in thermal catalysis which account for the specific differences and peculiarities of reactive catalysis compared to thermal catalysis.

In the following discussion, we propose that the surface electrical field is one of these critical features that differentiates mechanisms and reactive design from thermal catalysis. It is important to note that this aspect may be important in some cases but not in others. As concisely overviewed later, the role of the surface electrical field is also an emerging question in thermal catalysis. However, it plays a different role, and it is intrinsically different (including in mechanistic aspects) below a threshold temperature. Reactive catalysts operate in these conditions where the thermal energy is insufficient to overcome the energy necessary for the limiting energy barrier in the reaction. A different mechanism to provide the energy to overcome the energy barrier is thus necessary. This involved the strong localised electrical fields (LEF) generated by resonance (coupling) between surface charges and localised phonon modes (vibrations) of the catalyst. Localised phonon modes are possible when symmetry is broken, for example, by defects.

There is a parallelism between the existence of these localised phonon modes [54-57] and catalyst features (defects, steps, etc.), which are typically claimed as the active site [58-61]. There is recent evidence that electric field polarisation associated with defects determines electrocatalytic behaviour [62]. However, at high temperatures (i.e. during thermal catalysis), localised phonons are not possible and, thus, cannot be an effective coupling with charges to create strong LEFs. Thus, the proposed mechanism and role of LEF are feasible only under these conditions. Later, these aspects are better clarified. However, it is important to anticipate that when we discuss LEF, it is different from the conventional electrical field (less strong and localised), which affects the orientation of chemisorbed molecules and surface mobility [63-69]. The effect of an electrified interface on an electrolyte [70,71] and vice versa, the electrolyte influences on the interfacial electric field [72,73] are also different cases, as well as localised field confinement near metallic plasmonic nanostructures [74]. On the other hand, it is also worth mentioning that due to the complexity of catalysis, electric fields (and heterogeneity) are one aspect, but not the only one which determines the behaviour.

While the aim here is not to criticise the literature studies and their conclusions, we would only highlight here that a different, unconventional perspective in approaching reactive catalysis design is possible. We are aware that this is a personal vision and different opinions exist. There are only a few limited literature indications, as this alternative vision has only recently been proposed. Thus, extensive literature support is not present. Consequently, we do not claim that our ideas are correct and can be a single unified framework approach to reactive catalysis. We aim only to offer clues and suggestions for a possible rethinking of fundamentals to reactive catalysis. The complexity of bridging thermal and reactive catalysis requires new concepts and approaches. At the same time, likely, this approach will not cover all the aspects related to understanding reactive catalysis.

We focus attention particularly on electrocatalysis, with a case example of photo-catalysis, because these are the areas in which more active fundamental research exists. We believe that plasma catalysis shares most of the considerations made, but still, the understanding of surface catalytic processes after interaction with a non-thermal plasma (NTP) is in its infancy, and more effort in this direction is necessary [75].

1.1 The complexity of reactive catalysis design and understanding

Many aspects not currently properly accounted for in mechanistic studies (see comments above and related references) are instead crucial to describe and identify designing criteria for reactive (electro) catalysis. Among them, below are some relevant questions and observations:

- (i) Surface localised charges are generated by the application of a potential (in electro-driven processes), charge separation induced by light (in photoinduced processes), or interaction with the surface of NTP-generated charged molecules or hot electrons (plasma catalysis). These charges may accumulate or be stabilised at specific surface sites (nanoparticles, interfaces and heterojunctions, defects, strains, etc.). These surface processes are highly dependent on the nanostructure of the electrode. There is an inhomogeneous surface distribution of charges depending on the nanostructure, and the intrinsic reactivity of the surface charges is influenced by the nanostructure, including the recombination and redox reactions they induce. Today, advanced nanoscale mapping tools [76-79] show that the surface of electrodes is far from being homogeneous, even for simple planar electrodes. However, the relevance of these effects needs to be recognised in mechanistic studies, particularly in electro-chemistry.
- (ii) A consequence of the above comments is the presence of an electrical surface field associated with the electrode nanostructure. It generates local variations in the potential and nature of the double layer when an electrolyte is present. This fact can drastically influence the redox (electron transfer) processes, as commented in the first case example discussed below.
- (iii) In addition, the processes of charge generation, either electro or photo (likely also in plasma case), are very fast (femto to pico-second scale), while the surface redox processes of these charges to give rise to chemical reactions are much slower, in the milli-second range [80]. The latter is thus the limiting step, but due to the presence of possible side reactions (such as charge recombination) and the largely different timescale in the processes, the stabilisation of these charges at specific surface locations is crucial. The consequence is that as a function of the nanostructure of the electrode, local accumulations of charges are possible. Their presence is demonstrated by current nanoscale mapping methods (for example, by atomic force microscopy combined with a Kelvin probe or other method to monitor surface charge density at a nanoscale level [81-83]). However, the rate of the latter processes depends significantly on the local charge and, thus, on the nanostructure. What is often interpreted as a change in the nature of the active sites is, instead, possibly a physical effect connected to a change in local potential (related to changes in the local charge density) and associated electric field due to the nanostructure.
- (iv) The redox processes, both in electro and photo processes, are the slow step of the reaction. These processes occur through an inner- or outer-sphere charge (or energy) transfer to the incoming molecule (as commented later, inner- and outer-sphere are the commonly used mechanistic approaches in electro-chemistry [84,85]). Suppose an electro- or photo-catalytic process is present. In these cases, it is assumed (although typically not proven) that the chemisorption of the incoming molecule is faster, and the redox processes change from an

inner/outer sphere process to a surface process. Typically, in electro-chemistry, electron transfer (occurring through inner or outer sphere mechanisms) is faster than chemisorption, but in electrocatalysis, chemisorption must be faster than electron transfer. Otherwise, it is not possible to have a surface mechanism. Verification of this assumption is typically absent in most electrocatalytic mechanisms. It requires that i) the rate of chemisorption is faster than the rate of the inner/outer sphere redox process, ii) the surface redox process is faster than the inner/outer sphere redox process, and iii) the chemisorption site is near the site where charges accumulate. These assumptions are not very likely, particularly considering that most of the photo- and electro-catalytic processes are made at room temperature. Thus, it is not obvious that electro- and photo-chemical processes are instead electro- and photo-catalytic ones. At least, it has to be demonstrated. However, this crucial aspect is not addressed.

- (v) The mechanisms of photo- and electro-catalysis reactions assume that a catalytic process occurs. Even considering that this happens, the crucial step is the reaction between chemisorbed species and the surface localised charges. Besides the fact that modelling tools like DFT methods are not effective in describing such a type of reaction, they describe the energy profile of the possible paths/intermediates, assuming a specific surface configuration (typically obtained by cutting along some planes of the crystal). Then, the mechanism hypotheses are based on analysing the possible paths and identifying the lower energy. The process of transferring the energy necessary to overcome the barrier is not accounted for. Note that localised charges can be included in DFT calculations [86]. Still, the question here is different because it deals with charges trapped by resonance with localised phonons. Localisation of charge (polarons) often fails with DFT because of self-interaction errors inherent in typical exchange-correlation functionals; modifications for the approach are possible [87-89] but not typically made.

As commented above, heterogeneous (thermal) catalysis operates above a threshold temperature, where the thermal energy is sufficient to overcome the energy of the rate-limiting step. However, this is not typically valid in photo- and electro-catalytic processes operating at room temperature (in the absence of light or of an applied potential, the rate is virtually zero). There is, thus, a problem with how to transfer the energy for the surface transformation. This question is an aspect discussed later. There are thus two key questions in modelling approaches that are not addressed: i) how to describe the surface reaction between localised charges and chemisorbed species and ii) how to transfer the energy required to overcome the activation barriers in the surface catalytic processes. While there are also other aspects, these two crucial questions, in addition to those commented on above, questioned the validity of current mechanistic approaches to reactive catalysis.

It is thus evident that there are many open aspects, often ignored, in transferring the mechanistic and modelling approaches used for thermal catalysis to reactive catalysis. It is not only a question of complexity but also of intrinsic limitations that suggest the need to rethink fundamentals and develop new approaches to understanding and designing reactive catalysis. This objective is highly

challenging and beyond the possibilities to be fully demonstrated in this contribution. We thus aim only to stimulate the exploration of these aspects with a creative and open-minded approach.

1.2 Electron transfer, the crucial step

As emerging from the previous discussion, in reactive catalysis, different from thermal catalysis, the crucial step is the electron transfer from a mechanistic point of view, which determines the activity and selectivity. This is typical in electro-chemistry [90], at least in one-electron transfer. Theory of electrochemical reactions is based on electron transfer [91-93]. On the contrary, in photo-catalysis, the typical attention in terms of designing the catalyst is given to the previous and faster steps, the processes of charge creation and separation [94-98], including in terms of modelling. However, these steps determine the number of charges, not the intrinsic rate, which is related to the electron transfer and is not properly accounted. In electrocatalysis, the rate-limiting step is questioned [99-101]. It will depend greatly on whether or not it is a sequence of one-electron transfers (maybe coupled with proton transfer [102]) or rather multielectron transfer, which typically leads, however, to higher energy intermediates. However, it is critical that only a minority of the many studies on electro-catalysis experimentally prove (or even question) what the crucial step is, the electron transfer or, rather, a surface reaction. This question can be further clarified by the brief differentiation between electro and thermal catalysis and electro-catalytic vs electrochemical processes.

While electro-catalysis and electro-chemistry are often considered synonymous, they are associated with different reaction mechanisms. In electro-chemistry, the crucial step (determining the rate and eventually selectivity) is an electron transfer between the charged electrode and the incoming molecule (or vice versa). This electron transfer involves an inner- or outer-sphere mechanism [103-105]. The theory was originally developed for one-electron reactions. Two relevant cases are required to modify this theory: i) multiple electron transfer processes and ii) proton-coupled electron transfer [102,106,107]. The catalyst surface is not explicitly involved in these electrochemical mechanisms. When multiple electron transfer reactions are present, however, the energy of the product of multiple electrons (simultaneous) transfer may be too high that a cascade sequence of single electron transfer reactions is preferable. In these cases, the intermediates may chemisorb or be stabilised at the catalyst surface. In the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), this is the case for chemisorbed hydrogen species (H_{ads}) that generate H_2 through a concerted proton-electron transfer or reaction with a second H_{ads} species (Heyrovsky and Tafel steps). Thus, some aspects of catalysis are included in electrochemical approaches and modelling. Thus, even if the chemisorption could be included in electrochemical models, an effective description of surface catalytic reactions and their dependence on the active site and catalyst nanostructure is not effectively present.

In electrocatalysis, instead, a surface catalytic mechanism is used to model and understand the process, including the so-called Sabatier principle and its variations, e.g. that a volcano plot exists in correlating reaction rate and an activity descriptor [25,40,108,109]. This computational approach

does not effectively differentiate between catalysis and electrocatalysis and includes electron transfer as an effective crucial step. There is thus a gap on both sides in developing a unified electrochemical and electrocatalysis theory. On the other hand, there is also a gap between electro- and thermal catalysis. The latter usually also does not include considerations about electro-transfer as a crucial step.

1.3 Role of localized electrical field (LEF)

As shortly introduced above and further discussed later, we proposed that a characteristic feature of electro-catalysis (and likely of reactive catalysis) is the generation of strong localized electrical fields (LEF) deriving from the coupling of charges with localized phonon modes (i.e. when extended modes are breakdown by defects, presence of steps or interfaces, etc.). The role of electrical fields in altering and controlling surface catalytic reactions is also an emerging field in thermal catalysis [63,65,67,110-113]. Further examples are presented later. However, it is an additional effect (on the main catalytic path) that influences orientation in chemisorption, promotes/controls surface mobility, and polarizes transition state levels/intermediates/products, stabilizing them. The electric field is typically externally applied but could also be intrinsically present, even if it is typically weak. Strong LEFs could instead generated by coupling between localized phonon modes (thus related to typical features indicated often as active sites, i.e. defects, steps, interfaces, heterojunctions) and charges (generated by potential or other mechanisms). This resonance strongly localizes the charges and thus generates strong LEFs. These strong LEFs are suggested to determine the rate (and selectivity) in electron transfer processes, besides influencing the other aspects commented on above. Thus, they are a crucial aspect in understanding electro (reactive) catalysis and specific electro-catalysis compared to thermal catalysis, where the higher temperature avoids such a charge localization [114].

2. A case example: photocatalytic water splitting on TiO₂

The photocatalytic water splitting to produce "yellow" H₂ (e.g. produced directly using solar energy and as a more sustainable alternative to green H₂ produced by electrolysis) is an area that has received increased research attention in the last years, even if this possibility is known by decades back to the pioneering work of Fujishima and Honda in 1972 on TiO₂ [115]. Endless reviews, a limited selection of which is given in the following references [116-124], have discussed design criteria for photocatalysts for water splitting. TiO₂ is still a major photocatalyst investigated, with many attempts to improve, particularly its activity in the use of visible light.

It is not relevant here to discuss the abundant literature on this reaction and the many ways attempted to improve the performances. Still, using a photocatalytic "particulate" approach (i.e. using the photocatalyst in the form of powder; this term "particulate" is often used to differentiate photocatalytic processes where both redox reactions occur on the same photocatalyst particle, even if eventually at different crystalline faces, from the photoelectrocatalytic devices where the two redox reactions are physically separated at anode and cathode zones [119,125]), the solar-to-hydrogen efficiency is a maximum of about 1%, in contrast to photoelectrocatalytic solutions, e.g.

where the photoactive element generates a photocurrent which drives electrochemical water splitting [120,122]. In this case, 10% or more efficiency is possible [125], e.g. one order of magnitude larger.

In contrast, the particulate approach is simpler and less costly, even if there is a coproduction of O₂ and H₂, which are instead separately produced in photoelectrocatalytic solutions [119,125]. However, the crucial question, although not addressed in the literature, is why there is over one order of magnitude increase in efficiency, even using the same or similar materials. We may advance that the explanation is related to the more efficient mechanism of charge separation being physically separated anode and cathode present with respect to a particulate system where they occur on the same particle, eventually in different facets.

The important point is that by physically separating the anode and cathode, a potential is generated between them, which influences the rate of anodic and cathodic reactions, thus leading to an increase in the rate and efficiency of solar-to-hydrogen conversion. While it is surprising that this question was not analysed in the literature, being crucial to developing the next generation of solar fuel devices, we may use the above (tentative) interpretation to introduce the importance and role of creating a local potential or electrical field (the two aspects are interconnected) at the surface of the photocatalyst. This question is another aspect not explicitly addressed in the literature.

From a mechanistic perspective, in addition to directions to enlarge the fraction of light able to generate charge separation (band gap engineering, etc.), the different research directions and design criteria for water-splitting photocatalysts can be summarised in the attempt to improve the time of charge separation, limiting side recombination reactions and trapping the charges at specific surface sites, typically metal nanoparticles acting as "cocatalysts" [126]. These mechanisms can be viewed as ways to create local charge accumulation and, thus, a local potential/electrical field at the nanoscale going exactly in the direction commented above to explain the difference in the solar-to-H₂ efficiency between particulate and photoelectrocatalytic approaches. This mechanistic interpretation is completely different from those used in discussing design approaches for water-splitting photocatalysts.

In fact, very limited attention has been given to understanding the crucial limiting step of charge/energy transfer to protons to generate H₂ or of holes to water (or OH⁻) to generate O₂. Most of the design criteria, for example, exposed crystal facets, the use of cocatalysts and heterojunctions, charge-trapping mechanisms, defects engineering, etc., are different views to attain the same objective, although not explicitly identified: localise charges. How can we demonstrate that this aspect is critical to enhancing the rate of water splitting?

One of the few attempts to analyse this question is in the recent work by Verduci et al. [127]. In this work, the key aspect addressed was to understand how a change in the local electrical field at the surface of TiO₂, induced by B doping, determines a change in the local structure of the first layers of water at contact with titania. Here, attention was given to excluding the typical effects used to

explain enhancements in the water splitting rate, such as band gap, heterojunctions, crystal facets, etc.

The molecular structure of water is old, although still an actual question [128]. Liquid water is characterised by a dynamic assembly of clusters (average 8-9 molecules) of H-bonded water molecules. Different types of water molecules were identified [129,130], such as water H-bonded to other water (3483 cm^{-1}), non-H-bonded water (3559 cm^{-1}), Eigen protonated water (3059 cm^{-1}), Zundel protonated water (3371 cm^{-1}), etc. The frequency indicated is that of the O-H bond in these molecules, which allows for monitoring them (for example, by FTIR or Raman spectroscopy). The relative abundance of these molecules depends on various factors, from confinement effects to the interaction with a surface and the presence of a local electrical field.

Verduci et al. [127] analysed the nature of water in the first layers at contact with two samples of TiO_2 , doped or undoped with small amounts of B. These samples were carefully selected. The B-doped TiO_2 sample has a five times larger water splitting rate than the undoped, but an extensive characterisation proven than the conventional interpretation to explain the increase in water splitting activity by doping (changes in crystal facets, band gap changes, heterojunctions, etc.) are not valid or have an effect in the opposite direction, e.g. reduce the rate. On the other hand, extensive theoretical modelling has proven that the effect of B-doping induces a localisation in the charge accumulation during photo-catalysis and a change in the surface electrical field. These samples allow us to analyse the role of charge localisation and electrical field in water-splitting activity.

In B-doped TiO_2 , the nature of the water in the first water layers changes (e.g., in the Stern layer) with the formation of water molecules arranged into chain-like structures, as well as the creation of water dimers (Figure 1). Why this change is important?

The water structure near a solid surface influences the electron transfer reactions and electrocatalytic activity [131]. Marcus' theory on electrochemical processes and its extensions [103,132,133,105,104,134] indicates, in essence, that the electron transfer rate, especially in outer-shell electron transfer mechanisms, is determined from the solvent reorganisation and thus would strongly depend on the solvent's first layer (molecular) structure. The modification of the TiO_2 surface by doping, changing the surface electrical field and thus the nature of the first water layer structure, will thus influence the water splitting rate only when the water splitting process is controlled by outer-shell electron transfer, e.g. it is not a surface-dominated (catalytic) process. These results thus prove that the water-splitting process on TiO_2 is not photocatalytic but an electrochemical (outer-sphere) process with surface charge localisation generated by the light-activated charge separation in the semiconductor.

While further proofs are required to demonstrate and consolidate the general validity of this assumption, it is evident that it may completely change the current models of interpretation of water splitting at semiconductor surfaces and point out the difference between thermal and reactive catalysis. The design criteria for water-splitting mechanisms are tools to create surface charge localisations and associated potential/electrical fields. While the effect remains, the interpretation is

largely different. Thus, it turns out how these tools can be used for designing new photocatalysts and overcoming the gap discussed between particulate and photoelectrochemical approaches.

Figure 1. Water structure in the Stern layer of a semiconductor with different surface electrical fields (TiO_2 and B-doped TiO_2) and its impact on the rate of photocatalytic water splitting. Adapted with permission from ref. [127]. Copyright ACS, 2024.

This case example demonstrates how new concepts and approaches would be needed to understand and design reactive catalysts and to solve crucial open questions not properly investigated in the literature, mainly for the limit in identifying the gap between thermal and reactive catalysis. It is an emerging area, and other authors also recently observed similar effects, e.g. that by changing the surface of metal (Au) particles by alkali metals, there is an influence on the water structure in contact with them, and this markedly influences H_2 evolution reaction kinetics and efficiency [135]. They used scanning tunnelling microscopy and noncontact atomic force microscopy to visualise directly the nature of water in the contact layer. Still, they did not analyse why (by which mechanism) the change in the water structure impacted the reaction kinetics.

3. The role of surface electrical field and nanostructure

The previous section has introduced the concept that the main differences between reactive and thermal catalysis are i) the presence of surface charges which generate a local electrical field (potential) which can orient chemisorbing molecules or induce changes in the interface above the catalyst surface, and ii) the presence of additional possible mechanisms, e.g. inner- or outer-sphere charge/energy transfers, controlling the reactivity. The latter mechanisms are known in electrochemistry, but a "flat" electrode surface is considered. In electrocatalysis, we always have a nanostructure that determines the distribution of non-homogenous charge surfaces.

Kelvin Probe Force Microscopy (KPFM), e.g., atomic force microscopy (AFM) combined with the Kelvin probe method, is one of the methods, although still limited in use in electrocatalysis, to map the potential distribution on an electrode [136]. The lateral resolution of conventional KPFM is in

the 30-100 nm range due to Coulombic forces. However, by using a field-effect transistor to switch the electrical connectivity of the tip and sample on and off periodically, it is possible to improve the spatial resolution and also reach the high operational speed of the AFM tapping mode [137]. In addition, it is possible to combine with photoinduced force microscopy (PiFM) to characterise the nanoscale photoactive materials, semiconductors, and ferroelectric materials [137] (the latter is very relevant for plasma catalysis).

There are other methods to map the surface potential/electrical field distribution in reactive catalysts, for example, electrostatic force microscopy (EFM) [138] or reactive probing molecules and SEM (scanning electron microscopy) image brightness analysis [139]. Further examples were indicated before. Without being exhaustive, it is evident that there is a fast-growing series of methodologies, in continuous improvement, to map the nanoscale charge/potential/electrical field distribution in electrodes. These methods provide evidence that the approximation of a flat distribution is not realistic in most real cases, with the effective local situation different from the average value. Local differences in the charges can also induce enhanced surface transports, local microdischarges, local change in Fermi levels, and other possible effects that have not yet been investigated.

There are, however, some few attempts to explore these effects. Lv et al. [64] analysed how an electric field (EF) influences the catalytic behaviour but referred mainly to an externally applied EF to a single-molecule device. Bogaerts et al. [20] discussed instead the impact on the surface reactivity of an external EF or associated with plasmonic effects as part of the analysis of novel directions in unconventional catalysis. Spatial surface charge engineering was introduced as a novel concept for the design of functional surfaces of materials [140]. Modulating electric field distribution was introduced as a new possibility to tune and enhance the electrocatalytic behaviour in CO₂ conversion [141].

The roles of applying an external EF in catalytic reactions were analysed in a perspective paper by Che et al. [63]. They presented a series of experiments proving how an EF influences the catalyst selectivity using a variety of advanced experimental methods, such as pulsed-field mass desorption microscopes, scanning tunnelling microscopes, probe–bed–probe reactors, continuous-circuit reactors, and capacitor reactors. They also commented on cases where EF is not externally applied but intrinsically present. The role of built-in or external EFs in the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) was discussed recently by Feng et al. [142]. Xu et al. [62] investigated the relationship between the atomic-level polarisation in EFs of catalyst surfaces (defective monolayer MoS₂) and their electrocatalytic activity (hydrogen evolution reaction, HER). Luo et al. [143] showed that the local EF distribution in electrolytes depends on the spatial distance between nanoparticles, and this determines an order of magnitude increase in HER of spatially isolated and periodically distributed Pt nanoparticles (called by them mosaic catalyst) compared to uniform Pt films. Zhang et al. [144] showed how the introduction of a strong built-in EF (by fabricating Ni₂P-CoCH heterostructure) creates asymmetrical charge distributions on catalyst surfaces that enhance HER and OER

reactions. Huang et al. [145] proved that external EFs can tune catalytic selectivity by orienting the alignment of the EF along the axis of the activated bond.

Although these cited studies do not cover all the literature studies in the area, the role of surface EF in modulating catalytic behaviour, particularly in reactive catalyst trio materials, is evident. However, the effect of EF is also present in thermal catalysis, even if it has less impact, except when a strong external EF is applied. There is no unified strategy for designing catalysts based on these concepts, but the relevance in understanding the complexity gap between thermal and reactive catalysis emerges from these studies. It is not a unique difference but an aspect that is still not sufficiently adequately investigated and accounted for, particularly in mechanistic terms.

We can use these indications to offer alternative interpretations of results from the literature. For example, in electro and thermal catalysis, the active sites are often related to the presence of defects, interfaces, etc. Defect or interface engineering is a common design parameter [146-151]. The possibility that the behaviour is instead related to the change induced by the presence of these defects in the surface electrical field (particularly for reactive catalysis) is not considered. It is thus possible that the catalytic behaviour depends indirectly on the presence of these sites because they induce a change in the surface distribution of the potential. This could be the effect determining the behaviour in reactive catalysis, or it has to be proven that this alternative interpretation is not valid. In thermal catalysis, the reaction temperature minimises the relevance of these effects. This is another example demonstrating that translating thermal to reactive catalysis may lead to incorrect interpretations.

A few attempts have shown that the above interpretation is correct or at least has to be accounted for. The idealised plate-capacitor model typically used in electrocatalysis has to be improved by recognising that under an applied potential, the charge will accumulate in surface protrusions, leading to a local electric field enhancement. The effect is enhanced at protruding defect sites like steps and kinks, leading to significant changes in the dipole field and adsorption energies [152]. When an electrolyte is present, reorganisation of the electrolyte induced by the local electric field enhancement also occurs. The local field induces changes in the mass transfer through the electrical double layer and, consequently, in the kinetics of the process [153]. When a nanocatalyst is present rather than an ideal flat surface, gradients in the electrical double layer occur, influencing the mass transfer across the double layer and the surface mobility of adspecies [154,155]. Field-induced reagent concentration was proven to enhance the electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction [156,157]. Figure 2 shows that changing the local electric field in Au nanoneedles by modifying their curvature makes it possible to significantly affect the Faradaic selectivity in CO₂ electrocatalytic reduction [157].

The optimal performance in CO₂ electroreduction (CO₂RR) depends strongly on the interaction strength between adsorbed CO₂ and the local electric field. Various other studies have similar conclusions. For example, Zhao et al. [158] demonstrated the curvature effect in pyridinic N sites in carbon nanotubes and how it is correlated with the CO₂RR behaviour, concluding that the pyridinic N site forms a strong local electric field around the nearby C active site determining the

electrocatalytic behaviour. Vijas et al. [159] studied FeNC single-atom catalysts in CO₂RR, interpreting the results in terms of surface dipole moment and the dependence of activity on local field enhancements. Theoretical ab initio studies should also include the presence of a local electrical field and the role of the solvent dynamics near the electrode [160,161].

Figure 2. (top) Effect of Au nanoneedle tip radii of (A) 5 nm, (B) 10 nm, and (C) 15 nm on electric field concentration; a lower tip radius generates a higher electric field concentration. (bottom) Faradaic efficiency in CO₂ electroreduction to CO using different Au nanoneedles. Adapted with permission from ref. [127,157]. Copyright ACS, 2016.

Thus, there is growing evidence of the importance of the surface electrical field, how it is connected to the nanostructure and nanoparticle shape, and the importance of analysing the catalytic data. However, these aspects are often ignored when concepts are translated from thermal to electrocatalysis. For example, it is known that the shape and size of Cu nanocrystals influence both activity (current density) and faradaic selectivity in CO₂RR [162,163]. However, the results are typically interpreted in terms of the density of edge sites over the (100) plane sites.

Figure 3 illustrates this concept, presenting for Cu nanocubes (NC) the results reported by Loiudice et al. [162] in the correlation of the current density at -1.1 V vs RHE (reversible hydrogen electrode) against the size of the Cu NC catalysts, and the near electrical field (NEF) of NCs based on indications given by Montaño-Priede and Pal [164]. The results may also be correlated to the near-surface electric field induced by edge sites and the dependence on size besides shape. Thus, alternative interpretations that are more in line with the electrocatalysis effect, rather than those translated from thermal catalysis, could exist. However, they are not typically considered.

Figure 3. Correlation of the size of the Cu nanocubes (NC) with the current density in CO₂RR, the N_{edge}/N_{100} ratio (e.g. between edges and (100) sites) and the near electrical field (NEF) in cubic nanoparticles. Based on the data reported by Lojudice et al. [104] for CO₂RR and N_{edge}/N_{100} ratio, while by Montañó-Priede and Pal [106] for estimation of NEF.

The aim is not to criticise the literature's results, and more specific studies would be necessary. Here, we would only highlight that reactive catalysis requires the development of specific models and mechanistic approaches beyond those developed for thermal catalysis.

4. A new modelling approach for electrocatalysis?

A consequence of what was commented on above is the question of whether a new modelling approach for reactive catalysis would be necessary. Let's discuss electrocatalysis cases more specifically, but the discussion could be extended to photo and plasma catalysis.

Now, the use of DFT (density functional theory) and derived methods is a common practice in electrocatalysis mechanistic studies. The methodology is typically the same as that used for thermal catalysis without introducing specific features or characteristics related to electrocatalysis or, in general, electro-chemistry [165-167]. On the other hand, computational electrochemistry [134,168] attempts to include catalytic aspects, but it largely describes electrochemical rather than electrocatalysis mechanisms. Here, the point is not whether the accuracy of the theoretical methods is sufficient or how to improve computational predictions [169] but whether a completely different theoretical approach than DFT and related methods would be necessary in light of the comments above. In a nutshell, the DFT method (in a simplified definition) allows for the estimation of an optimal energetic profile typically going from the chemisorbed reactant to the final product. It is based on considering a static surface situation typically based on cutting at specific planes the crystalline structure of the catalyst particles. It does not consider how the energy to overcome the activation barrier is provided because, in thermal catalysis, the temperature is enough to provide the energy for the reaction. The catalyst design information is thus associated with proof that the hypothesised active sites provide the minimum possible surface pathway of transformation.

The case for electrocatalytic is different. First, the reaction temperature is below the threshold for catalysis (at least in typical cases). Thus, without the application of a potential, the reaction does not occur. Usually, the potential applied is largely above the thermodynamic potential to have the electrochemical reaction, e.g. a significant overpotential (in practical cases) should be applied to have a sufficient current density (productivity). Interestingly, at the typical applied overpotentials (above 0.6-0.8 V, but also significantly higher depending on the cell [170]), many reactions are possible, for example, in CO₂RR [171-173]. From this viewpoint, it cannot be understood why good Faradaic selectivities are possible in many cases. It may be argued that the role of the catalyst is to provide the selective surface path of transformation. However, it cannot be explained why the reaction rate depends on the overpotential applied. This common observation already questioned whether the model of interpretation should be different.

Before discussing this point, it is worth discussing whether there is evidence in the literature of the limits of current methodological approaches in the identification of mechanisms and design criteria for electrocatalysis. There are not many studies attempting to evaluate this question. We have analysed a set of literature results on a homogeneous set of catalysts for the electrocatalytic fixation of N₂ (based on doped carbon materials) [6,50] and CO₂ conversion to methane (on copper-based catalysts [51]). The papers have been selected because they arrive at completely different mechanistic hypotheses, even if the electrocatalytic performances (current density and Faradaic efficiency) are quite similar as well as the electrocatalysts are analogous. Each article provides a consistent set of experimental and theoretical results that prove the proposed mechanism. However, how can completely different mechanisms lead to very comparable performances in a set of catalysts with homogeneous characteristics? The derived indication is that the factors determining the electrocatalytic performances are different from those identified, and the indicated reaction mechanism does not determine the performances [52,51,53]. Thus, the design criteria for their improvement should also be different from those that can be derived using theoretical modelling for the analysis of mechanistic aspects, such as morphology, crystallographic facet, defect engineering, and others.

Is it possible to conceive a different theoretical approach for reactive catalysis? There are no effective developments or attempts in this direction, but a possibility to explore may be proposed. The key points are how to i) provide the energy for the selective path of conversion selectively, ii) account for the specific characteristics of reactive catalysis, e.g. the presence of localised charges and associated effects, and iii) consider the electrocatalyst nanostructure and the aspects discussed related to the dependence of the potential/electrical field from the nanostructure. These are the aspects not accounted for in the current modelling approaches for electrocatalysis mechanisms and should be considered in a novel computational method.

Selectivity in energy transferring to the adsorbed molecule determines the transformation pathway, while this aspect is not considered in current electrochemical theoretical approaches. The combination of a suitable energy profile and a selective mode of energy transfer will realise the control of the selectivity in electrocatalytic reactions.

In electrocatalytic processes, the energy to overcome the activation barrier has to be associated with the potential that generates localised charges. In general, the energy transfer to the incoming or adsorbed molecule occurs by coupled electron and energy transfer, eventually coupled with proton transfer (PCET) [174,175]. The energy transfer should involve solid vibrations (e.g., surface phonon), being how a solid can transfer energy to an adsorbed molecule [176,177]. Surface phonons are well-studied in solid-state physics. They are the quantum of a lattice vibration mode of a solid surface [178,179], with the energy transfer occurring through the coupling of molecule bond vibrations with the solid phonons. This process can be modelled through an extension of the Langevin dynamics [180].

The general question is that these surface phonons (being typically delocalised) do not have sufficient energy to overcome the activation barriers and, thus, normally do not play a role in thermal catalysis. However, when the symmetry is broken down due to the nanostructure and/or the presence of defects, and the localised phonons interact with localised charges (electron-phonon and exciton-phonon bound states [181-183]), the energy could be in the range relevant to have selective energy transfer [184], similar to what occurs in coupling phonons with hot charges generated for example by plasmonic effect [185,186]. Localised phonons generate at point or extended defects, step edges, twin boundaries, etc. [187-190], e.g. the sites typically considered as the active ones. There is a clear dependence on the nanostructure, as well as a clear dependence on the applied potential, charge distribution, etc.

Surface phonons may also interact with strong localised electrical fields, generating polaritons (hybrid particles made up of a photon strongly coupled to an electric dipole). These excited states have been proposed for controlling selective pathways of conversion in molecules whose high-frequency vibrational modes are strongly coupled with them [191,192]. The coupling between excitons and phonons enhances the local electrical field [182], which induces a strong electron-phonon coupling that traps the excitons [193].

Even if a theory of localised phonons and their interaction with surface charge in determining the selective energy transfer and pathways in electrocatalytic has not yet been developed, it is evident that the bases exist to reconsider the theory of modelling electrocatalysis mechanisms and design criteria. In other words, develop a specific theoretical framework for reactive catalysis which accounts for their specificity and is not the simple translation from thermal catalysis.

Figure 4 visually introduces the difference between the conventional approach used in thermal catalysis and the possible approach based on selective energy transfer through local solid excited states generated by the interaction with localised phonons and surface charges or excitons.

Figure 4. The conceptual difference between the conventional approach used in modelling electrocatalytic reactions (mediated from heterogeneous catalysis) (right graph) and the novel modelling proposed based on localised surface phonons (left graph). The right graph is based on the indications of Wang et al. [194] used as an example for modelling the electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction (CO₂RR). The figure on the right is a visual presentation of the results reported by Autore et al. [195].

5. Conclusions

Addressing the complexity of bridging thermal and reactive catalysis requires the development of new concepts and approaches. While there are increasing pieces of evidence sheering light on the difference between what we call reactive catalysis (photo, electro and plasma catalysis) and conventional thermal (heterogeneous) catalysis, the concept still finds resistance to being accepted. Most of the mechanisms and design criteria are largely based on translating the thermal catalysis methodologies and concepts to reactive catalysis. We anticipate that an effective acceleration in the field of photo, electro and plasma catalysis could be achieved when the difference from thermal catalysis is properly identified and specific methodologies accounting for this difference are taken into account.

It is not only a matter of additional complexity in the phenomena but of the need to reconsider and rethink reactive catalysis from the perspectives outlined above. Even revise the fundamentals, e.g. the mechanistic approaches and the factors controlling the design.

We presented here some case examples and concepts related to photocatalytic water splitting on TiO₂, the role of strong LEF deriving from the coupling of localized phonon modes (related to nanostructure, defects etc.) with surface charges generated in the typical processes related to reactive catalysis (application of a potential, generation of charge separation by light adsorption, etc.). These indications suggest the need for a new modelling approach for electrocatalysis accounting for the differences between electro (reactive) and thermal catalysis. It will likely not be a unifying theory for all catalysis, given the complexity of the problems, reaction conditions, and

systems analyzed. Nevertheless, it is suggested as a crucial element to consider for a novel design of electro (reactive) catalysis.

It has to be remarked that only scattered observations are present in the literature, without a general consensus on the aspects presented here, being a very recent area and still needing to grow as both modelling and experimental evidence. However, we think that it is necessary to look at the problem of reactive catalysis from a different perspective than thermal catalysis and recognise the difference. The aspects discussed offer food for thought to clarify this crucial question to accelerate the progress in the field.

The aim is thus to put this difference under the spotlight and stimulate researchers, particularly the younger ones, to investigate the difference creatively and develop novel methodologies.

Competing Interests

The authors declared that there are no financial or non-financial interests directly or indirectly related to this contribution.

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